

Improving the Combustion Characteristics and Emissions Using Nano Titanium Oxide Additive to Biodiesel

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Abstract-- It is vital to find alternative fuels to reduce fuel consumption and to reduce exhaust emissions. Biodiesel was produced from waste cooking oil through a process of transesterification. Waste cooking biodiesel physical and chemical properties were measured in accordance with ASTM standards. Biodiesel blend was produced by mixing diesel and biodiesel by volume percentage of 20% as W20. TiO₂ nano additive was mixed with biodiesel at 25 mg / l, 50 mg / l and 100 mg / l as 25, 50 and 100 ppm. The aim of this paper is to evaluate the performance and exhaust emissions of diesel engines using a biodiesel blend using nano additive. Tests were carried out on a diesel engine with different engine loads at rated speed of 1500 rpm. Biodiesel blending with nano B20T100 resulted in the highest improvement in BTE and decrease in BSFC by 8.5 and 7% relative to biodiesel blend. Nano additive with waste cooking biodiesel B20T100 achieved the highest reductions in CO, HC, NO_x and smoke emissions by 22, 33, 15 and 37% relative to B20. Addition of nano TiO₂ to biodiesel blend improved the combustion characteristics related to B20. Biodiesel blend with nano additive concentration of 100 ppm achieve maximum enhancement in performance, combustion characteristics and emissions about biodiesel blend.

Keywords: Waste cooking oil, Biodiesel, TiO₂, Performance, Emissions, Combustion characteristics.

1. Introduction

The application of nano-particles to diesel fuel has been undertaken by numerous researchers to enhance performance and minimize pollution in diesel engines. In order to improve the performance of biodiesel and ethanol blends, an additional analysis of ZnO nanoparticles has been conducted [1]. Investigation of the impact of diesel water emulsions and nanotechnology on diesel engines has been investigated [2]. The introduction of nano fluids reduced the emissions and increased combustion efficiency. BTE, NO_x and smoke were improved by the usage of zinc oxide nano-materials as an additive to diesel fuel [3]. The introduction of zinc oxide nanoparticles to palm oil biodiesel raised BTE, NO_x and EGT and reduced CO, HC and smoke emissions [3, 4]. The effect of alumina and silica nanoparticles on butanol-diesel blends improved the diesel engine performance, reduced soot emissions and raised CO and NO_x emissions relative to diesel fuel [5].

The impact of the introduction of zinc oxide nanoparticles to diesel oil was studied. BTE was increased with the increase in ZnO nanoparticles in fuel [6, 7]. CNTs addition to biodiesel blends improved the output brake power by 3.67 % and BTE by 5.57 %. There were reductions in SFC, CO, HC and soot [8]. Nano additives to fuels have enhanced thermo-physical properties such as high surface to volume ratio, thermal conductivity. Nano additives with biodiesel blends improved the flash point and kinematic viscosity [9, 10, 11]. Aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) and copper oxide (CuO) nano-particles were applied to diesel fuels and the combustion characteristics were enhanced with the usage of nano-diesel blended fuels [12]. CNTs were blended with Jojoba methyl ester diesel blends on the performance and emissions of CI engine have been studied. Enriching of fuel with CNTs produced an improvement of 16% in the thermal efficiency and a reduction of 15% in SFC about diesel oil. NO_x, CO and HC were reduced by 35%, 50% and 60, respectively [13, 14].

The large surface area of soluble nano-sized catalyst particles resulted in combustion and emissions improvement. Engine power and torque were improved by 7.81 and 4.91 %, respectively, and fuel consumption decreased by 4.5 % [15-17]. The usage of CNTs led to NO_x decline by 45 %, CO by 50 % and HC by 60 %. The maximum dose level of 40 mg / l was developed to boost the engine performance [18-20]. The temperature of the exhaust gas was increased and the thermal efficiency was decreased for biodiesel blending. The involvement of oxygen in soybean biodiesel and the enhanced mixing capability of nanoparticles greatly decreased CO and HC emissions [21-26]. Cerium oxide nanoparticles serve as an oxygen- catalyst that provides oxygen for CO oxidation and absorbs oxygen for NO_x reduction. Through the introduction of cerium oxide nano particles, the emissions of hydrocarbons and NO_x were decreased. The enhancement in thermal efficiency and emissions reductions were due to air-fuel mixing improvement and accelerated evaporation [27].

An experimental study was performed on the combustion properties of alumina nano-particles of 13 nm average size dispersed with biodiesel jatropha [28, 29]. The test results showed that the evaporation rate, longer-term stability and better combustion properties were shown. The application of 25 to 50 ppm of alumina nano particles to jatropha biodiesel contributes to a substantial improvement in

engine performance and emissions reductions [30-33]. The performance of C.I.E. by introducing cobalt oxide and iron oxide nanoparticles to jatropha biodiesel in a mixed proportion of 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60 parts per million were analyzed [34-38]. Specific cerium oxide doses of 20, 40, 60 and 80 ppm were used to obtain an optimum mix. Flash point and viscosity of biodiesel were improved by the introduction of nanoparticles. NO_x and HC pollution levels were greatly reduced [39]. The introduction of cerium oxide nanoparticles enhanced the flash point, volatility and increased the viscosity [40, 41].

The goal of the present research is to evaluate the engine performance and exhaust emissions of diesel engines utilizing titanium nano oxide blended biodiesel oil. Waste cooking oil was selected as an economical and available feedstock. The use of nano TiO₂ because of its lower cost compared to other additives. WCO biodiesel blend with nano additives were prepared by dispersing nano additives in biodiesel blend at concentrations of 25, 50, 100 and 200 ppm and compared to diesel fuel. Performance parameters such as specific fuel consumption, thermal performance, exhaust gas temperature and air-fuel ratio had been tested and compared to diesel oil. Exhaust pollutants such as CO, NO_x, HC and smoke pollutants for blended biodiesel with nano-additives were compared to diesel fuel.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Biodiesel production process

Waste cooking oil had been obtained from hotels, restaurants and manufacturers. The oil was refined and purified from impurities. The oil was preheated to a temperature of 70 ° C to remove the moisture. The oil was dissolved in methanol at a molar ratio of 6:1 using NaOH catalyst and the mixture was stirred continuously. Upon completion of the transesterification, the mixture was permitted to settle in a separating funnel under gravity for 24 hours. The glycerol was drained and the oil methyl ester was cleaned with water to eliminate the unreacted methoxide. Biodiesel was then heated to eliminate the water in order to produce transparent biodiesel [1, 7-9]. Waste cooking biodiesel was mixed with diesel oil in volume percentage of 20% as B20. The calculated physical and chemical properties of biodiesel blends had been shown in Table 1. The calorific value of biodiesel is smaller than that of diesel oil. Measured cetane number of biodiesel is greater than crude diesel. Biodiesel flash point is greater than petroleum diesel.

Table I
Physical and chemical properties of waste cooking oil biodiesel compared to diesel fuel according ASTM standards.

Properties	Method	Diesel oil	B100	B20	B20T100
Density at 15.56 °C	ASTM D-4052	829	883	832	832.5
Kinematic Viscosity at 40 °C	ASTM D-445	1.2	3.8	2	2.5
Flash Point, °C	ASTM D-93	70	120	73	----
Lower heating Value, kJ / kg	ASTM D-224	42000	39278	41500	-----
Cetane Number	ASTM D-13	45	47	56.5	-----

2.2 Preparation of biodiesel nano blends

Nanotech Egypt company provides nano titanium oxide (TiO₂) with its specifications as shown in Table 2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) offered a detailed analysis of its alignment and size. Nano-particle morphology was investigated through Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) (Model: Quanta FEG250) in Central Laboratories, National Research Centre, Egypt. The surface and morphological characterization of nano additives were performed using Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) (Model: JOEL JEM-2100). The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and the transmission electron microscope (TEM) for nanoparticle were seen in Fig.1. TiO₂ nanoparticles had been spread into B20 biodiesel blend. The fuels were prepared by dispersing each nanoparticle separately in mass fractions of 25, 50 and 100 ppm of biodiesel blends. Nano particles had a higher surface contact area and higher surface energy. Nano particles had been grouped together to create a

micromolecule and proceed to settle. Nano particles surface were modified. Ultrasound is a method to distribute the nanoparticles in the fluid and avoid the agglomeration using pulsating rates. A continuous constant agitation of 30 minutes time was used to achieve an uniform distribution. Nano-additive blended fuel should be used directly after preparation to prevent the sedimentation [5, 6, 7, 9, 10]. In order to reach a dosing level of 25 ppm, 0.025 g of each nanoparticle was applied to 1 liter of biodiesel blend. The produced nano particles biodiesel mixtures were named as B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100. The surfactants Span80 and Tween80 had been used to spread the nano-particles in biodiesel blend for stability improvement. XRD of nano TiO₂ showed the crystallization at a peak at $2\theta = 24.78$ as shown in Fig.2 (a) [42]. FT-IR analysis was used to show molecules structure of TiO₂ as bands which indicated the transmittance of the sample as shown in Fig. 2(b). O-H vibration mode was observed as 3420 cm⁻¹ and 1617 cm⁻¹ bands [43]. The band of 1261 cm⁻¹ was matched with Ti-

OH stretching band. The lattice vibrations of TiO₂ were showed in bands between 800 and 400 cm⁻¹ [44, 45].

Fig. 1. SEM and TEM photos of TiO₂

(a) Titanium dioxide nano particles XRD (b) TiO₂ nano particles FTIR

Fig. 2. XRD and FTIR configurations of TiO₂

Table II
Nano particles properties

Properties	TiO ₂
Manufacturer	Nanotech company, Egypt
Appearance (color)	White
Appearance (form)	Powder
Solubility	Dispersed in Water
Avg. Size (TEM)	35 ± 5 nm
Shape	Spherical

2.3 Experimental set up

The tests were conducted on a single-cylinder, four-stroke diesel engine with a maximum output power of 5,775 kW at 1500 rpm. The engine specifications were listed in Table 3. The schematic description of the experimental system was displayed in Fig. 2. The engine brake power was calculated by an AC generator with a nominal electrical output of 10.5 kW coupled directly to the test engine. The intake air flow was calculated using a sharp standard edge orifice held on the side of the air box to dampen the pulsating air flow. A U-tube manometer was used to measure the pressure drop across the orifice. The temperatures at different locations in the experimental set up were used to measure the intake air and exhaust gases by using thermocouple probes of type K. OPA 100 smoke

meters and MRU DELTA 1600-V gas analyzer were used to test smoke emissions and exhaust gas concentrations such as CO, HC, CO₂ and NO_x. A Kistler piezoelectric pressure transducer of model 601A with a pressure range from 0 to 250 bar and a frequency of 16.5 pc / bar was connected with Nexus charge amplifier of model 2692-A-044. The instantaneous location of the piston top dead center was calculated using a proximity switch of model LM12-3004NA. The cylinder pressure was estimated over 120 consecutive engine cycles. The combustion parameters were acquired by data acquisition card NI-USB-6210 using LABVIEW software. Experiments were performed at varying engine loads from zero to maximum load at a steady rated speed of 1500 rpm during the experiments.

Table III
Engine specifications

No.	Engine parameters	Specification
1	Engine model	DEUTZ FIL511
2	Number of cylinders	1
4	Cooling type	Air cooled
5	Bore, mm	100
6	Stroke, mm	105
7	Compression ratio	17.5:1
8	Fuel injection angle	24° BTDC
9	Rated brake power, kW	5.775 at 1500 rpm
10	Number of nozzle holes	1
11	Injector opening pressure, bar	220

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|----------------------------------|------------------------------------|
| 1. Diesel engine | 10. Piezo pressure transducer |
| 2. AC generator | 11. Charge amplifier |
| 3. Diesel tank | 12. Data acquisition card |
| 4. Fuel tank | 13. Personal computer |
| 5. Burette | 14. Exhaust gas analyzer |
| 6. Air surge tank | 15. Smoke meter |
| 7. Orifice | 16. Exhaust gas temp. thermocouple |
| 8. Pressure differential meter | 17. Proximity switch |
| 9. Intake air temp. thermocouple | 18. Cardan shaft |

Fig. 3. Schematic diagram of the experimental setup.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Engine performance

Figure 4 demonstrates the impact of the introduction of TiO_2 nano additive with concentrations of 25, 50 and 100 ppm in B20 at various engine loads. BSFC becomes lower as the engine load rises at all fuels due to the fuel consumption increase. Relevant fuel consumptions at the same loads were lower than waste cooking biodiesel blend

and diesel oil. The explanation for this is due the presence of oxygen molecules coupled with TiO_2 . Addition of nano additive improves atomization and promotes combustion. BSFC values for diesel, B20, B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100 were 0.27, 0.34, 0.33, 0.32 and 0.315 kg/kW.hr, respectively at full load. These results were agreed with references [19, 29, 41].

Fig. 4. Specific fuel consumption for tested fuels at different loads.

The thermal efficiencies output for all fuels at engine load variation were seen in Fig.5. The increase of BTE associated with the engine load increase. Thermal efficiencies for nano additives blended with biodiesel blend were improved relative to ethyl ester mixture. The thermal efficiency was improved by enriching of TiO_2 nanoparticles in fuel blends, indicating combustion enhancement and the successful transfer of fuel energy to

useful work. The increase of the surface to volume ratio of nano-particles improved the fuel vaporization and atomization. Higher viscosity and lower calorific value of biodiesel related to crude diesel led to lower BTE and higher BSFC. Tested fuels produced thermal efficiencies of 30, 23, 24, 24.5 and 25%, respectively for diesel, biodiesel blend and nano concentrations of 25, 50 and 100 ppm at 100% of load as displayed in the review [28, 39, 41].

Fig. 5. Effect of TiO_2 nano additives on thermal efficiency at load variation.

Figure 6 displayed the exhaust gas temperatures for pure diesel, B20, B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100. The exhaust gas temperature (EGT) increased with the change in the load. This change could be attributed to the higher cylinder temperature and more fuel consumption to satisfy the higher load requirement. EGT for biodiesel was higher than petroleum diesel due the heat loss increase. The application

of TiO_2 nanoparticles to B20 has contributed to a decrease in exhaust gas temperature. Nano particles contribute to better combustion and higher engine thermal efficiency, which reduces the loss of enthalpy in the exhaust. Exhaust gas temperatures for diesel oil, biodiesel blend and B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100 were 275, 305, 300, 290

and 280°C, respectively at full load as confirmed by results [28, 41].

Fig. 6. Exhaust gas temperature for tested fuels at different loads.

3.2 Engine emissions

Variations in carbon monoxide emissions with the engine load for all tested fuels were shown in Fig.7. For all measured fuels, there is an increase in CO pollution with the rise in engine load from part load to maximum load. This is attributed to the increase in fuel consumption, which contributes to a rich fuel- air mixture and incomplete combustion. Compared to diesel fuel, a substantial decrease in CO emission over the entire engine load was found when biodiesel and its blends were used. CO concentrations

decreases were primarily attributed to a higher level of biodiesel oxygen than fossil diesel, which contributes to accelerated combustion and less CO emissions. TiO₂ had a higher surface contact area that improved the chemical reactivity, which consequently reduced the ignition delay. The degree of fuel-air mixing was increased due to TiO₂ additive. Burning of crude diesel, B20, B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100 produced CO values of 0.045, 0.043, 0.039, 0.037 and 0.035 %, respectively at full load as agreed with literature [27, 39, 41].

Fig. 7. Influence of tested fuels on CO emissions at different loads.

Figure 8 demonstrates the impact of diesel, biodiesel waste cooking oil, B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100 on NO_x emissions. NO_x emissions increased with the engine load increase due to the higher cylinder combustion temperature and higher adiabatic flame temperature. NO_x development is favored by the higher combustion temperatures, oxygen content and higher cetane number. NO_x levels are found to

be higher for biodiesel than fossil diesel due to the oxygen present and higher cylinder temperature. The concentration of NO_x becomes lower as the concentration of nanoparticles increases. Lower air entrainment and air fuel mixing for nano fuel blends resulted in lower cylinder temperature and NO_x values compared to pure biodiesel blend. Diesel oil achieved NO_x emission value of 77 ppm.

Biodiesel blend and nano additives of 25, 50 and 100 ppm showed NO_x values of 82, 75, 72 and 68 ppm, respectively as confirmed with the results [18, 27, 29].

Fig. 8. Nitrogen oxide emissions for the tested fuels at different loads.

Figure 9 demonstrates the HC emissions values for diesel, waste cooking biodiesel blend, concentrations of 25, 50 and 100 ppm. HC emissions for all combusted fuels are seen to be lower at partial engine load, but increased at full engine loads. The shorter ignition delay associated with higher cetane number reduced the over-mixed fuel and unburned hydrocarbons for biodiesel related to pure diesel. The oxygen content in biodiesel lowers the HC concentrations

about diesel fuel. Adding different concentrations of nano-additives to waste cooking oil biodiesel B20 contributes to better vaporization, enhanced fuel air mixing and catalytic reactivity, both of which result in lower hydrocarbon emissions compared to ethyl ester blend. HC concentrations for crude diesel, B20, B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100 were 35, 33, 32, 30 and 29 ppm at 100% of load as shown with review [17-19].

Fig. 9. Effect of nano additives on HC emissions at load variation.

Variations of smoke emissions for all tested fuels were displayed in Fig.10. There is an improvement in smoke percentages with the rise in engine load for all fuels. It is attributed to the increase in fuel usage at rich combustion. The decrease in smoke density emissions for waste cooking oils B20 about diesel oil due to oxygen content and combustion improvement. Waste cooking biodiesel blend with nano-additives showed decreases in smoke value

attributed to the presence of more oxygen molecules, higher surface to volume ratio and improved combustion characteristics about biodiesel blend. Burning of crude diesel, ethyl ester blend and nano concentration blended with WB20 (B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100) achieved smoke values of 42, 41, 39, 38 and 36 %, respectively at full load [27-29].

Fig. 10. Smoke emissions at different loads for nano additives blended with biodiesel.

3.3 Combustion characteristics

In-cylinder pressure variations versus crank angle for diesel, B20, B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100 at full load were shown in Fig.11. The greater the engine load, the greater the in-cylinder pressure due to the more fuel consumed. Biodiesel blend showed decrease in cylinder

pressure about diesel oil because of shorter ignition delay and less fuel burned in premixed stage. TiO_2 contributed to an improvement in the cylinder peak pressure due to the higher thermal conductivity, evaporation speed up, enhanced combustion and greater contact surface area. The presented oxygen in biodiesel improved the combustion.

Fig. 11. Cylinder pressure versus crank angle at full load.

Variations of peak cylinder pressures with engine load for all fuel mixtures were shown in Fig.12. The peak pressure was directly proportional to the engine load. The improvement in engine load contributes to the decrease in the ignition delay, which results in an advance of the

combustion. At full load, the peak cylinder pressures of the fuel tested are reported as 71, 65, 67, 68 and 69 bar for diesel, B20, B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100 blends, respectively at full load as agreed with the literature [39, 41].

Fig. 12. Effect of nano additives on peak cylinder pressure at load variation.

The Variations in the rate of heat release of all fuels at different crank angle were shown in Fig.13. Heat release rate for biodiesel is lower than pure diesel due to lower cylinder pressure. The heat release rate of B20 with nanoparticle blends has the same pattern with biodiesel blend. The shorter ignition delay, the properties of the nano-additives improved combustion. Including

nanoparticles raises the peak cylinder pressure due to accelerated release of heat during combustion. The peak heat release values for diesel, biodiesel blend and nano additives concentrations of 25, 50 and 100 ppm were 51.28, 45, 46, 47 and 48 J/Degree, respectively at full load as confirmed with review [39, 41].

Fig. 13. Heat release rate versus crank angle at full load.

Figure 14 shows the variation of calculated in-cylinder temperature versus CA at full load for tested fuels. This can be found that the average cylinder temperature for biodiesel blend was less than diesel oil due to lower calorific value and lower cylinder pressure of biodiesel related to diesel. The application of nanoparticles to B20, the in-cylinder

temperature increases. This can be due to the decrease of ignition delay and combustion improvement. The average mean cylinder temperatures indicated as 1270, 1000, 1030, 1080 and 1160 K, for diesel, B20, B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100, respectively.

Fig. 14. Cylinder temperature at different crank angles and full load.

3.4 Performance, emissions and combustion characteristics comparative analysis

Table 3 provides a summary of the percentages deviations of performance parameters, emissions and combustion characteristics for B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100. The improvements in BSFC, BTE and EGT were shown with the application of nanoparticles to diesel-biodiesel mixtures. The maximum decreases in specific fuel consumptions for B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100 were 0.8, 8.4, 9.8 and 11.6 %, respectively, relative to ethyl ester blend. The highest increases in thermal efficiencies for ethyl ester blend with nano concentrations of 25, 50 and 100 ppm were 1.8, 10.3, 12.1 and 14.4 %, respectively, relative to biodiesel mixture. The exhaust gas temperatures highly decreased by about 28.9, 13.5, 11.5 and 17.5 % for B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100, respectively, relative to biodiesel blend. These results showed that addition of nano particles to B20 gave a better engine performance.

CO emissions were highly decreased by up to 13, 16 and 22% for biodiesel waste cooking oil with nano additives concentrations of 25, 50 and 100 ppm, respectively, relative to ethyl ester blend. The maximum decreases in HC levels for B20T25, B20T50 and B20T100 were 14, 22 and 33% about biodiesel blend. The highest declines in smoke levels were 14, 25 and 37 %, respectively for nano additive concentration of 25, 50 and 100 ppm relative to B20. The maximum increase of CO, HC and smoke emission for crude diesel about B20 was 7, 12 and 33%. The maximum decrease in NO_x emission for diesel about ethyl ester blend was 17%. It is evident that the exhaust emissions were lower for waste cooking bio-diesel with nano-additives. The highest improvements in cylinder pressure at full load were 10, 3, 6 and 8% but the heat release rate achieved maximum increases as 14, 2, 4 and 6% for diesel, B20T25, B20T50, and B20T100, respectively relative to biodiesel mixture. The highest enhancements in cylinder temperatures for diesel and B20 blend with nano concentrations of 25, 50 and 100 ppm were 25, 3, 8 and 16%, respectively compared to biodiesel blend.

Table III
Engine performance comparison for biodiesel blend with TiO₂ about B20.

No.	Performance	D100	B20T25	B20T50	B20T100
1	Specific fuel consumption	-27%	-3.5%	-5.5%	-7%
2	Thermal efficiency	+25%	+4.5%	+6.5%	+8.5%
3	Exhaust gas temperature	-11%	-3%	-5%	-8%
4	Emission of CO	+7%	-13%	-16%	-22%
5	NO _x emission	-17%	-8%	-12%	-15%
6	HC emission	+12%	-14%	-22%	-33%
7	Emission of smoke	+33%	-14%	-25%	-37%

8	Peak cylinder pressure at full load	+10%	+3%	+6%	+8%
9	Peak heat release at full load	+14%	+2%	+4%	+6%
10	Peak cylinder temperature at full load	+25%	+3%	+8%	+16%

4. CONCLUSIONS

Waste cooking oil was converted to biodiesel. WCO biodiesel properties were evaluated. Performance, exhaust emissions and combustion characteristics of biodiesel waste cooking oil blended with the nano-additive TiO₂ were examined in a single cylinder diesel engine. The current study evidence summarizes as follows:

- Decreases in specific fuel consumptions and thermal efficiencies were noted with the introduction of biodiesel with nanoparticles. Biodiesel blending with nano B20T100 resulted in the highest improvement in BTE and decrease of BSFC by 8.5 and 7% relative to biodiesel blend.
- Nano additive with waste cooking biodiesel B20T100 achieved the highest reductions in CO, HC, NO_x and smoke emissions by 22, 33, 15 and 37% relative to B20.
- The maximum improvements in cylinder pressure at full load were 10, 3, 6 and 8% but the heat release rate achieved maximum increases by 14, 2, 4 and 6% for diesel, B20T25, B20T50, and B20T100, respectively relative to biodiesel mixture. The highest enhancements in cylinder temperatures for diesel and B20 blend with nano concentrations of 25, 50 and 100 ppm were 25, 3, 8 and 16%, respectively compared to biodiesel blend.
- Biodiesel blend with nano additive concentration of 100 ppm achieve maximum enhancement in performance, combustion characteristics and emissions about biodiesel blend.

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